

Research Article

Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers

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Abstract: *Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers has been developed to focus on how these improvements address everyday travel encounters and meet the diverse needs of travellers to travel in style. One such innovation is incorporating a smart light to improve visibility in poorly lit environments and offering a convenient light source for searching traveller's belongings. In addition, the travel bag includes USB ports connected to internal power banks, allowing users to charge their devices on the go while the bag remains unpacked. This bag is similarly innovative, with access to indispensable items such as a telekung (prayer garment) and a sejadah (prayer mat). An innovative travel bag designed with multiple compartments for storing these items can greatly enhance the convenience and ease for Muslim travellers. This travel bag is also designed to address both the demand for reduced tiredness and more mobility, while also ensuring the safety of personal things through its sturdiness. It is also unique because the travel bag is made from Terengganu Batik motifs. A comprehensive market survey was conducted to evaluate the Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers, utilizing both social media platforms and direct interactions with potential buyers of the travel bag. Based on the feedback and responses from the participants via the face-to-face survey, it is evident that they highly appreciate the design and functionality of Perfect 10 Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Travellers. The continuous collaboration with PPDK Wakaf TAPAI promotes sustainable cultural, social, and economic development in the local community, aligning with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This initiative demonstrates a successful model of community-based sustainable development and positions the Batik Travel Bag as a travel compulsion item.*

Keywords: travel bag; versatile bag; traveller; travel behaviour; explorers.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The travel industry has seen significant transformations in recent years, driven by technological advancements and consumer behaviour shifts. Modern travel bags now have improved ergonomic designs, and sustainable materials, catering to the needs of the contemporary traveller who values convenience and security.

Consequently, Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers has been developed to focus on how these advancements address common travel challenges and meet the diverse needs of

travellers. One such innovation is a smart light within this innovative travel bag. This feature addresses various needs, from improving visibility in poorly lit environments to offering a convenient light source for searching travellers' personal belongings. Travelers often find themselves in situations where adequate lighting is unavailable, such as during late-night arrivals, camping, or accommodations with insufficient lighting. Studies by Wilson and Carter (2021) indicate that poor lighting can significantly impact travellers' comfort and safety, making portable lighting solutions highly desirable. Traditional portable lamps, however, can be cumbersome and inconvenient to carry, highlighting the need for integrated solutions.

In addition, integrating technology into travel accessories has become a significant trend, driven by the need to keep mobile devices powered and accessible during travel. Smith and Jones (2022) state that travel bags with integrated charging capabilities are becoming increasingly popular in the smart travel bag industry. Thus, Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers features USB ports connected to internal power banks, allowing users to charge their devices without unpacking their bags. As the demand for connected travel accessories continues to grow, these smart travel bags are poised to become an essential part of the traveller's toolkit.

Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers, also innovated with having access to essential items such as a telekung (prayer garment) and a sejadah (prayer mat). An innovative travel bag with multiple compartments for storing these items can greatly enhance convenience and ease for Muslim travelers. According to Ahmed and Yusuf (2021), the need for easily accessible and clean prayer items is a significant concern for many Muslim traveller's. Traditional travel bags often do not cater to these specific needs, leading to inconvenience and added stress.

Besides, travellers require bags that are not only lightweight to ease the burden of carrying but also sturdy enough to protect their belongings throughout the journey. This travel bag is also designed to address the demand for reduced tiredness and more mobility, while ensuring the safety of personal things through its sturdiness.

Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers is also unique because the travel bag is made from Terengganu Batik motifs. Terengganu Batik, known for its intricate patterns and vibrant colours, is a significant cultural symbol of Malaysia, particularly the Terengganu region (Abdullah and Hashim, 2021). Integrating this traditional textile into travel bags not only preserves and promotes cultural heritage but also adds aesthetic value and uniqueness to the product. Notably, these collaborative initiatives and innovations involving members of the disabled community from PPDK Wakaf Tapai can contribute to economic sustainability while fostering social responsibility and inclusiveness. This project can foster creativity, skill development, and community engagement while providing opportunities for disabled people's income generation and market participation. This innovation project is significant not just in its promotion of social entrepreneurship among individuals with disabilities but also in its provision of meaningful experiences, particularly for those who engage in travel. The discoveries of the innovation project will enhance the effectiveness of government projects and initiatives. The mentioned policies and plans are the National Entrepreneurship Policy (NEP) 2030, the Malaysian Plan of Action for People with Disabilities (MPAPD) 2016–2022, the 12th Malaysian Plan (RMK12), and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Study Approach

This innovation project uses the Liberatory Design Thinking Method. Liberatory Design Thinking is an equity-centred design framework developed by Anaissie et al. (2017), to expand the familial design thinking process. While design thinking is divided into five phases: empathise, define, ideate, prototype, and test (The Interaction Design Foundation, n.d.), liberatory design thinking includes two additional phases: notice and reflect, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Process Conducted to develop Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers

2.1.1 Notice Stage

The Notice phase of the Liberatory Design Thinking Framework promotes self-awareness among stakeholders, designers, and decision-makers. It requires comprehending their values, identities, biases (unconscious, conscious, and subconscious), assumptions, and impacts on end-users or learners. Before proceeding with the project, the initial action was to assemble a design team. Historically, the design team comprised individuals selected from the Special Interest Group (SIG), encompassing experts in subject matter, content creation, and design concepts.

2.1.2 Empathize Stage

The innovation team gathered data using ethnographic methods such as observations, interviews, and focus group discussions. They collected information from local people likely to travel frequently in a year (at least five times a year). The innovation team concentrated on asking questions that promoted liberation, leading to more in-depth and significant data collection, as demonstrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Liberatory questions for the Empathy phase (Self-Design)

Liberatory Question for the Empathy Phase
1. What are the core needs of the traveller?
2. What do you like/ dislike about the current product?
3. Do you think the product is effective?
4. How will the product help the customer?
5. This bag uses batik—how does it promote cultural awareness and support local batik producers?

2.1.3 Define Stage

Figure 2 shows how the innovation team synthesised and articulated the findings by creating travel bag personas criteria and empathy maps in the Define phase. During this phase, the design team narrowed the Notice and Empathy data to a visualisation of the traveller's needs.

Figure 2. An empathy map showing a traveller's needs (Self-Design).

2.1.4 Ideate Phase

The session was a discussion with PPKD Wakaf TAPAI, the person in charge of the Perfect 10 Journey Genius bag production, as a collaborator. The discussion includes the bag's design, colour, budget, and production schedule.

2.1.5 Prototype Phase

Material and product selection for the travel kit exclusive, including the fabric to be used, the label to be pasted, and the products to be included in the travel kit. The OKU trainee from PPDK Wakaf TAPAI initiated bag production as the final step in the Perfect 10 Journey Genius bag production stage after all innovators and collaborators had agreed.

2.1.6 Test Phase

The final stage of product development is testing, which refers to the potential buyer and user of the innovative product market survey. In this survey, the innovators are interested in the potential buyer's perception, acceptance, and intent to purchase the Perfect 10 Journey Genius Bag.

IDEATE	PROTOTYPE	TEST
<p>Discussing with PPDK Wakaf Tapai staff</p>	<p>Prototype Production</p>	<p>Google Form Market Survey and Final Product</p>

Figure 3. Photos related with Liberatory Design Thinking of Perfect 10 Journey Genius Bag

2.1.7 Reflection Phase

The design team at the non-profit organization incorporated reflection as an essential part of the liberatory design framework by creating an assessment plan. During the reflection phase, the following protocol have been practiced:

1. Anonymous feedback forum for team members who prefer anonymity.
2. Information can be collected through interviews, anonymous surveys, and focus groups. To feel safe, team members can share their experiences in any format.

3. Encourage non-judgmental communication and active listening without interruptions when someone shares their thoughts, feelings, frustrations, or pain points.
4. Respecting diverse perspectives and lived experiences without personal remarks.
5. Examine the design process and user feedback to identify areas where the solution failed marginalised communities or systemic issues.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Following discussions with team members, collaborators, and ten (10) passionate travel and batik enthusiasts, improvements were made to the previous travel bag. In light of these improvements, the team decided on the name of the travel bag, "Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Bag for Explorers."

Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorer embodies a blend of cultural artistry and practical functionality, designed to meet the diverse needs of modern explorers. This travel bag stands out for its exquisite batik patterns while offering robust features that cater to the demands of adventurous travel. It offers five (5) distinct and inventive characteristics that make it versatile.

Firstly, this travel bag is equipped with a specifically designed USB port, which serves multiple practical and convenient functions:

1. **Portable Charging:** The user can connect a power bank, which is kept inside the bag, to the port. Then, they can plug their device into the external port for convenient charging while on the go.
2. **Organisation:** It facilitates the arrangement of the charging infrastructure. One can conveniently connect the device to the external USB port instead of searching through the bag to locate the power bank and cable.
3. **Convenience:** It offers a high level of convenience, particularly during travel or commuting. The device can be kept in a traveller's hand or pocket while it is charging, eliminating the need to hold the power bank separately.
4. **Safety:** It can improve the devices' safety by minimising the frequency of bag opening and closing, thereby reducing the risk of theft or accidental drops.

Figure 4. USB Port

Secondly, it features a dedicated compartment that enables Muslim women to conveniently carry their telekung (prayer garment) and sejadah (prayer mat) in one bag, enhancing convenience and facilitating travel. Thirdly, adding an interior light improves ease of use and allows travellers to locate their belongings easily. Furthermore, Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers provides ample storage compartments for personal belongings such as wallets, mobile phones, and

hygiene kits, making it a versatile and all-inclusive accessory. Lastly, it is furnished with a sturdy and durable handle capable of supporting a load of more than two bricks.

Figure 5. Telekung and Sejadah Compartment, Interior Light, Multiple Compartment, Sturdy and Durable Handle

3.1 Market Survey

A comprehensive market survey was undertaken to evaluate the Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers, utilising both social media platforms and direct interactions with potential buyers of the travel bag. The main goal was to collect valuable information on the perception and acceptance of the product by both respondents and potential buyers. Questions asked to the participants:

1. What is your opinion on Perfect 10 Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers?

"The bag is practical for travellers, with excellent craftsmanship and a beautiful design that incorporates both modern and cultural elements, specifically batik. These features allow us to preserve and keep utilising batik." (Participant 1).

"From my point of view, the bag is particularly unique due to the various elements that strongly influence my decision to purchase it." The bag features a spacious compartment ideal for female travellers who enjoy carrying all their belongings in a single bag. Additionally, it is a versatile bag that can be used for both travel and work purposes. Furthermore, the bag possesses a fashionable and intelligent design, characterised by its simplicity and inclusion of an electric component, specifically a USB port. This feature allows me to charge my phone while travelling or working conveniently." (Participant 2).

"This bag is ideal for travel as it has a dedicated compartment for a telekung (prayer garment) and multiple compartments for other belongings. I like the interior lighting feature as it facilitates the retrieval of belongings in dimly lit areas, which is particularly useful during my camping trips. The presence of a USB port is highly convenient for me to charge my phone. Additionally, I particularly love the handle, as it allows me to use the bag as a sling bag." (Participant 3).

"From my viewpoint, the bag exhibits an appealing design and pattern. The item exhibits meticulous craftsmanship and features practical compartments, which is particularly beneficial for me as a mother who frequently travels with a baby. The bag appears to be established and has a value for commercialisation. This bag can be described as neat, aesthetically pleasing, and highly functional for the traveller." (Participant 4).

Based on the feedback and responses from the participants via the F2F survey, it is evident that they highly appreciate the design and functionality of Perfect 10 Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Travellers.

4. CONCLUSION

Overall, the creation of Perfect 10 Journey Genius: Batik Travel Bag for Explorers, which features Terengganu batik designs and is made by individuals with disabilities, is an impressive combination of cultural tradition, inclusivity, and functionality that is well-suited to the needs of today's society. This unique collaboration not only celebrates the rich artistic traditions of Terengganu but also showcases the creativity and talents of disabled artisans, promoting social inclusion and economic empowerment. The integration of a smart light into a travel bag represents a promising innovation that aligns with the growing demand for multifunctional travel accessories. The travel bag's multifunctional design addresses travellers' diverse needs in the new era, offering convenience, versatility, and style. With dedicated compartments for essential items such as mobile devices and charging ports, prayer garments, and sejadah (prayer mat), the bag ensures seamless organization and accessibility. This travel bag that includes both a lightweight construction and a solid design provides several advantages, including enhanced ease of movement, increased durability, and adherence to weight restrictions. In conclusion, incorporating Terengganu motifs into the innovative travel bag adds a touch of cultural authenticity and aesthetic appeal, making the bag a distinctive and meaningful accessory for travellers.

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